

Cyber-physical Product-Service Systems – Challenges for Requirements Engineering

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1 Nowadays, manufacturing industries need to
2 improve both their business offer and their
3 technological base, in order to make a more
4 sustainable value proposition, to be more efficient
5 and effective on the market, and to satisfy the user
6 needs. Significant emerging technologies discussed
7 in research are a networked and smart
8 environment connected by Internet of Things (IoT),
9 wearable technologies, tangible interfaces, human-
10 robot collaboration, evolving tools, processes and
11 interactions, avatar-quality VR, ubiquitous usage
12 of machine learning and deep learning algorithms.
13 These will increase the benefit of technology and
14 open the way towards technical breakthroughs,
15 leading to the emergence of Cyber-Physical
16 Systems (CPS). They can be seen as systems of
17 systems, requiring the collaboration of different
18 disciplines such as mechanical engineering,
19 electrical engineering, and computer science for
20 their realization. To enable the full potential of CPS
21 and generate substantial competitive advantage
22 however, the service perspective cannot be
23 neglected. Servitization of product offerings has
24 recently cumulated in so-called Product-Service
25 Systems (PSS), which describe the integrated
26 development, realization and provision of product-
27 service bundles as a solution for the customer. Thus,
28 it is more and more important to consider both
29 technological as well as service aspects early in the
30 development process. An integration of the two
31 concepts would lead to product-service bundles
32 provided on a cyber-physical basis, creating Cyber-
33 physical Product-Service Systems (CPSS). In order
34 to base these complex systems on stakeholder needs
35 and allow a successful and dynamic change to CPSS
36 in industry, multi-disciplinary Requirements
37 Engineering (RE) for the product, IT and service
38 components is key. The objective of this paper is to
39 give a first description of the CPSS concept,
40 understand its application in an industrial case and
41 elaborate the specific challenges for systems
42 engineering, focusing on the RE process.

43 **Keywords:** Cyber-Physical Systems, Product-Service
44 Systems, Cyber-Physical Product-Service Systems,
45 Requirements Engineering

46 1. Introduction

47 Industrial companies are a set of human
48 competencies, skills and machine technologies able to
49 realise complex processes. In order to be more and
50 more competitive on the market, such processes are
51 based on economy of scale principles [1] and involve
52 globally distributed partners [2]. In this way, the
53 supply chain can be seen as an ecosystem of several
54 actors with different needs and able to share different
55 knowledge, acting and interacting in a dynamic
56 environment [3].

57 Rapid technological changes combined with a
58 highly competitive market have induced a need for
59 implementing new processes and production methods
60 for reducing “time to market” [4,5], waste and failures,
61 as well as in order to be both appropriate in terms of
62 quality and cost effective [6] and meet the customers’
63 expectation. For example, Follett [7] enlists as
64 significant emerging technologies a networked,
65 intelligent world connected by Internet of Things (IoT),
66 involving robotics, the usage of additive fabrication
67 and 3D printing, and promoting the just-in-time
68 production. The relevance of these technological
69 advances has been recognised by being implemented
70 in several governmental programmes like the German
71 “Industrie 4.0” paradigm [8,9] and the United States
72 Smart Manufacturing Leadership Coalition (SMLC)
73 [10] aiming at introducing Cyber-Physical Systems
74 (CPS) into manufacturing [11]. CPS emphasize the
75 link between computational and physical elements,
76 representing a network of interacting elements with
77 physical input and output instead of as standalone
78 devices. They require the collaboration of disciplines
79 such as mechanical engineering, electrical engineering,
80 and computer science for their realization [12].

81 However, the changes are not restricted to the
82 technological side, but companies’ business models
83 are also shifting from selling products to the provision
84 of integrated solutions. As Customers increasingly
85 demand support for all phases of the product life-cycle,
86 from development over assembly and distribution to
87 operation, a wide range of services is added to the
88 physical product in order to deliver new personalized
89 functions and other benefits. This trend has originally

1 been named as the “Servitization” of business [13] and
 2 led to the introduction of Product Service Systems
 3 (PSS) as a promising framework describing the
 4 integrated development, realization and offering of
 5 specific product-service bundles as a solution for the
 6 customer [14,15]. Offering of a PSS requires on the
 7 one hand additional competencies for the provision of
 8 the associated services and on the other hand a better
 9 understanding of the customer requirements. As the
 10 requirements now have implications on the whole
 11 product life-cycle, an integrated development of the
 12 physical product, services, and the manufacturing
 13 processes is needed.

14 The integration of CPS and PSS concepts is
 15 becoming relevant for industry due to the diffusion of
 16 pervasive Information and Communication
 17 Technologies (ICT), which have strongly reduced the
 18 cost for additional sensors and cloud technologies,
 19 enabling data monitoring, storage and processing [16].
 20 This allows creating a higher service layer able to
 21 deliver products with new “intelligent” behaviours and
 22 communicating capabilities (i.e. monitoring the
 23 surrounding environment, monitoring the users’ habits,
 24 interacting with other connected devices, being
 25 adaptable to the user needs, behaviours and attitudes)
 26 [17]. These developments represent new challenges for
 27 industrial companies above all in the design process,
 28 creating individual CPS based solutions for the
 29 customer, but also offering these solutions as a PSS
 30 with the appropriate services along the life-cycle. In
 31 this paper, we use the term Cyber-physical Product-
 32 Service Systems (CPSS) [18] for such an integrated
 33 approach.

34 The main prerequisite for successful and cost-
 35 effective systems engineering is understanding the
 36 underlying needs, and the thus the requirements on a
 37 solution throughout its entire life cycle [19–21]. In this
 38 context, it is essential to investigate and identify the
 39 requirements of the CPSS to design. For this reason, a
 40 suitable Requirements Engineering (RE), which aims
 41 to understand and capture stakeholders’ needs and
 42 related requirements, is the foundation to allow a
 43 successful and dynamic change to CPSS in
 44 manufacturing industries. A major challenge in this
 45 process is the integration of the product, service and
 46 ICT perspective, each having own models, methods
 47 and tools for RE. Process complexity is further
 48 increased by the higher number of stakeholders, the
 49 coverage of the whole life cycle [22], and the dynamic
 50 of functionalities expected by the customers, leading
 51 to evolutionary changes in the requirements.
 52 Continuous interaction between the CPSS
 53 development process and RE is inevitable for ensuring
 54 a consistent and traceable elicitation and management
 55 of requirements [23].

56 The objectives of this paper are to give an outline of
 57 CPS and PSS based on the state-of-the-art, aggregated
 58 to a first description of the CPSS concept; to elaborate
 59 its specific challenges for systems engineering,
 60 focusing on the RE process; to understand CPSS

61 application in an industrial case; and finally to derive
 62 the open issues and ways to overcome them.

63 The next section (2) will first describe the research
 64 approach and will identify the main research questions.
 65 Section 3 contains the literature review about CPS and
 66 PSS, while section 4 presents the description of the
 67 CPSS concept, as well as RE approaches in literature
 68 and their suitability for CPSS. Section 5 shows the
 69 involvement of two different use cases that
 70 demonstrate industrial applications of the CPSS
 71 concept. Section 6 defines remaining challenges for
 72 RE during CPSS Engineering. Finally, section 7
 73 concludes the research and presents next steps.

74 **2. Research Questions and Approach**

75 The main question to be answered in this paper is
 76 what are the challenges of RE for CPSS and how can
 77 companies be supported to successfully develop and
 78 offer such solutions? For this we first need to know
 79 what characterizes CPSS and which characteristics are
 80 relevant for the RE process. Secondly, which RE
 81 approaches exist and which limitation do they have.
 82 Based upon such analysis, we can identify the gaps of
 83 existing tools and framework for CPSS.

84 This leads to our research questions:

- 85 *i.* What is the state-of-the-art in CPS and PSS
 86 research and how can it be applied to
 87 establish the concept of CPSS?
- 88 *ii.* How can a CPSS be characterized and which
 89 existing RE approaches could be adopted?
- 90 *iii.* Which are the open issues and challenges of
 91 RE for CPSS and how could they be
 92 overcome?

93 In order to address these points, our methodological
 94 approach is based on combination of the research
 95 methods literature review and analysis of industrial use
 96 cases.

97 The literature review has been conducted by
 98 accessing scientific papers through the
 99 multidisciplinary SCOPUS database, as CPS and PSS
 100 are a cross-domain research topic. For practical
 101 reasons, the search was limited to books, journal and
 102 conference papers in English language. As several
 103 expressions are used in literature to describe the
 104 concepts, we searched for Cyber-Physical System,
 105 CPS, Product-Service System and PSS combined with
 106 Requirements Engineering, RE in titles, abstracts and
 107 keywords. The search results were checked for
 108 relevance and redundancy by assessing the abstracts.
 109 Based on this, papers were selected for in-depth
 110 analysis of the content. The literature review was
 111 complemented with papers from additional sources,
 112 such as Google Scholar. The work with the industrial
 113 use cases for CPSS had a different methodical
 114 approach. The researchers have been involved in the
 115 specification and development of the scenarios. More
 116 specifically, action research was applied [24].

1 **3. Theoretical Background**

2 This chapter identifies the specific characteristics of
 3 Cyber-Physical Systems and Product Service Systems
 4 related to systems engineering. Indeed, chapter 5
 5 presents real industrial case studies where the
 6 approaches described in paragraphs 3.1 and 3.2 are
 7 applied to design a new CPSS. This allows deriving
 8 challenges for the Requirements Engineering of CPSS.

9 **3.1. Cyber-Physical Systems**

10 CPS integrate physical capabilities with Information
 11 and Communication Technology (ICT) and offer new
 12 ways of human-machine interaction using advanced
 13 sensors and actuators (see Fig. 1). They require the
 14 collaboration of different disciplines such as
 15 mechanical engineering, electrical engineering, and
 16 computer science for their realization. Additionally,
 17 for reaching the full potential of CPS, the system will
 18 also comprise the logistics and management processes,
 19 as well as internet services receiving, processing and
 20 analysing data from the sensors and controlling the
 21 actuators, connected by digital networks and multi-
 22 model human-machine interfaces. As such, CPS are
 23 open socio-technical systems with a functionality far
 24 exceeding controlled embedded systems. [12]

25
26 **Fig. 1.** Cyber-Physical System

27 Several characteristics can be identified that
 28 describe CPS and distinguish them from other complex
 29 systems. The eponymous aspect of CPS is merging the
 30 physical and virtual world. CPS involve a multitude of
 31 parallel and interlinked sensors, computers, and
 32 machines, which collect and interpret data to decide on
 33 this basis and control real world physical processes.
 34 Thus, systems engineering needs to integrate industrial
 35 process and control systems with information
 36 technology [25]. Secondly CPS have dynamic system
 37 borders. Depending on application and task, different
 38 CPS are arranged into a system of systems for a limited
 39 time. Consequently, CPS have to be able to actively
 40 configure services and networks with other systems or
 41 part of systems, which may be unknown in the
 42 beginning, and provide new and composite
 43 components and services in a controlled way [26].
 44 Furthermore, an important characteristic of CPS is
 45 their ability to adapt to environmental changes and
 46 application requirements. This requires continuous
 47 monitoring and assessment of environmental and
 48 application data [27]. Additionally, in most cases,

49 there will be no central control of a CPS. Decisions are
 50 made locally based on an assessment of the situation
 51 and lead to a cooperative learning process [28]. Finally,
 52 CPS have to interact with humans also on a physical
 53 level, which requires multimodal control interfaces,
 54 recognition, and interpretation of human behavior and
 55 interactive decision making between the system and
 56 single persons or groups [29].

57 **3.2. Product-Service Systems**

58 The PSS concept focuses on the bundling of
 59 products and services. Indeed, it is defined by several
 60 researchers as a mix of tangible products and
 61 intangible services designed and combined to increase
 62 the value for customers [13,30]. According to that, the
 63 value creations is realized through the extension of the
 64 current business network, involving different
 65 stakeholders having the knowledge and skills required
 66 to design, develop and deliver an integrated PSS value
 67 proposition (see Fig. 2.).

68
69 **Fig. 2.** PSS and its main items

70 During the recent years, clear evidence shows that
 71 service plays an increasingly important role in many
 72 manufacturing industries. As an immediate
 73 consequence, especially the industry for complex
 74 products has moved from selling products to delivering
 75 product-service bundles. The Servitization process is a
 76 fundamental mean for manufacturing companies to
 77 find new business opportunities and involve new
 78 customer segments, increasing their market share
 79 [31,32]. This phenomenon concerns the evolution
 80 from selling a product (based on its ownership) to
 81 selling its usage (e.g. renting, pay-x-use, etc.) or
 82 performances (e.g. pay-x-performance).

83 Indeed, for a long time, producers have considered
 84 as the principal source of innovation the monetary
 85 profit derived by selling products and services. Within
 86 the last decades, users are an important complementary
 87 source of innovation, and their motivation to innovate
 88 is driven by their own needs and expected benefits
 89 from using the innovation rather than monetary profit
 90 expectations.

1 From the environment viewpoint, PSS provides a
 2 more conscious product usage, thanks to the service
 3 functionalities delivered, increasing resource
 4 productivity and a close loop-chain manufacturing
 5 [33]. From the economic viewpoint, PSSs are able to
 6 create new market potentials and higher profit margins,
 7 and can contribute to higher productivity by means of
 8 reducing investment costs along the lifetime as well as
 9 reducing operating costs for the final users [15].

10 The PSS and the related Servitization process extend
 11 the responsibility of the PSS provider to the whole life-
 12 cycle [34]. Moreover, Product Lifecycle Management
 13 (PLM) and Service Life-cycle Management (SLM)
 14 must be combined. In literature, Stark defined a first
 15 lifecycle model of an offer (tangible or intangible
 16 offer), distinguishing between product activities and
 17 service activities, but not their interactions [35]. For
 18 this reason, Peruzzini et al. [36] proposed a first
 19 example of Product-Service Lifecycle Management
 20 (P-SLM), which is able to fit the definition of PLM and
 21 SLM interactions, analysed in literature.

22 According to Stark, 2011 23 According to Peruzzini et al., 2014

24 **Fig. 4.** The transition from PLM and SLM to P-SLM

25 Usually manufacturing companies have well-
 26 defined and structured product development processes,
 27 but they lack a sufficiently in defining service
 28 development processes. Therefore, they are poorly
 29 equipped with appropriate approaches, methodologies
 30 and tools for supporting the development of PSS in an
 31 efficient way. Despite several methodologies have
 32 been proposed in literature to support industrial
 33 companies to design a PSS along its entire lifecycle
 34 [37], some of them are very theoretical and hard to
 35 implement in practice, others are very specific and
 36 have a limited applicability range. Anyway, in the last
 37 years few authors have studied a new design approach,
 38 integrating several existed methodologies to design a
 new PSS solution along its P-SLM [38].

39 **4. CPSS and Requirements Engineering**

40 This chapter first introduces the CPSS concept as a
 41 combination of CPS technology with PSS business
 42 models. Secondly existing RE approaches for systems
 43 engineering are identified and analyzed for their
 44 applicability on CPSS.

45 **4.1. Cyber-physical Product-Service Systems**

46 To unleash the full potential of CPS, the business
 47 perspective has to be involved besides the technological
 48 challenges in a very early phase. This means to define
 49 integrated services for a PSS offer already during the
 50 development of the CPS. The optimal combination of
 51 human resources, ICT, product and service components
 52 has to be managed and offered to the market through a
 53 suitable business model. An example are service
 54 aggregators that collect single services from different
 55 providers and offer them as an integrated solution on
 56 their platform. Their success depends on a focus on
 57 customer benefit, integrating the mentioned elements
 58 from the value network. Such integration of product
 59 and service through CPS is defined as a Cyber-physical
 60 Product-Service System (CPSS) [18].

61 In principle, the relation between the CPS and the
 62 PSS concept in a CPSS can be seen as interdependent,
 63 or symbiotic. When looking from a CPS perspective,
 64 the physical and ICT domains are complemented with
 65 service engineering for the development of the solution.
 66 This increases the number of stakeholders and adds
 67 additional domain-specific models, methods and tools
 68 to the development process. As a result, complexity
 69 rises, because every service element has to be aligned
 70 with all physical and ICT elements of the CPSS.

71 From the PSS perspective, the new cyber-physical
 72 functionalities are enablers of additional innovative
 73 services and business models. As such, the extended
 74 technical opportunities have to be taken into account
 75 when ideating new services that enhance customer
 76 benefit. Furthermore, the possibility to measure usage
 77 and performance of the CPSS allows for business
 78 models beyond a one-time sale. The customer can have
 79 a guaranteed availability of the system for a certain time,
 80 or even pay for the outcome of its application.

81 The above considerations can be summarized to a
 82 first illustration of the CPSS concept. The core is an
 83 intelligent product, similar to the processor hardware of
 84 the CPS. Here, it is however not reduced to its
 85 computational capabilities, but comprises all the
 86 tangible aspects of the offer, such as design and haptics.
 87 Similarly, it is connected to sensors, actuators and
 88 communicators, which enable its interaction with its
 89 environment (see Fig. 5.).

90 **Fig. 5.** The CPSS Concept

91 In the CPSS concept however, they are used to offer
 92 “basic services” such as monitoring, control and data
 93

1 processing. This internal structure is obscured to the
 2 outside world by a halo of high-level and non-ICT
 3 services. In the halo, the basic services are aggregated
 4 with the non-ICT services to fulfill certain
 5 functionalities and tasks. These high level services are
 6 not hard-wired into the CPSS and can change
 7 dynamically to new demands. Through this service halo,
 8 the CPSS is able to collaborate with different entities to
 9 achieve its intended aim. Those entities can be other
 10 CPSS, CPS just providing basic services, or even 3rd
 11 party services not directly developed for the system.

12 On the other hand, customers can pay for access to
 13 the high level services and use them for their benefit,
 14 e.g. ordering a pre-defined milling capacity. They can
 15 also work together with the CPSS provider to re-
 16 develop services specific to their needs. The same is
 17 true for suppliers of hard- and software, who are
 18 involved in the development of the CPSS and deliver
 19 spare and refurbishing components according to
 20 dynamic requirements. Finally, external service
 21 providers develop new services specifically for the
 22 CPSS, or use standardized interfaces to connect
 23 existing services.

24 Adequate Requirements Engineering is a crucial
 25 methodology to adopt during the design process of a
 26 CPSS, in order to identify the main requirements for
 27 the system according to the individual problem. Indeed,
 28 offering CPSS instead of traditional products requires
 29 additional competencies to identify the service and
 30 ICT functionalities to enhance the product, and a better
 31 understanding of the customer requirements to reach.
 32 This implies a huge quantity of implicit domain
 33 specific knowledge to be elicited and a big variety of
 34 actors to involve [39].

35 4.2. Requirements Engineering Approaches

36 Requirements Engineering describes a process
 37 where the needs of one or many stakeholders and their
 38 environment are established to find the solution for a
 39 specific problem [40]. This implies that the
 40 stakeholders' needs as well as the context in which the
 41 solution will be applied have to be analyzed in deep.
 42 Indeed, customers' and users' satisfaction depends on
 43 the fulfillment of the relevant requirements by the
 44 proposed solution. Furthermore, the RE process is
 45 characterized by a lot of interactions and environmental
 46 influences, which must be integrated into the extraction
 47 and evaluation of the requirements.

48 The purpose of RE is to understand the problem that
 49 arises from the needs of stakeholders, including, but not
 50 limited to, customers and end-users and transform it
 51 into requirements to define and design the related
 52 solution. This means that the RE focus is about the
 53 interaction of the solution with the problem, and not the
 54 behavior of the solution itself. Following the CPSS
 55 description, the RE approaches applied to this specific
 56 concept must be able to define requirements for a rising
 57 amount of product, service and ICT components, from
 58 both a growing number of distributed stakeholders and
 59 multiple disciplines. Consequently, only RE

60 approaches being able to deal with the complexity of a
 61 CPSS, its openness and evolutionary nature can be
 62 considered as suitable. Furthermore, due to the
 63 complexity of the problems to be solved, it also has to
 64 enable direct involvement of the user and information
 65 exchange between different stakeholders.

66 Geisberger and Broy [12] give RE a central role for
 67 CPS development, integration, maintenance and
 68 evolution. Several initial approaches from embedded
 69 system / CPS development could be identified.
 70 Hauksdóttir et al. [41] investigate the management of
 71 requirements for complex systems or products. They
 72 recognize requirement reuse as an enabler to increase
 73 efficiency and quality of Requirements Engineering
 74 and propose a structure for a reusable requirement
 75 specification. The proposed structure has five groups
 76 of requirements (business requirements, standards and
 77 laws, product properties, life phase requirements,
 78 design constraints) that are applicable to different
 79 products. Each group contains several sub-groups that
 80 have to be defined for each product individually and
 81 contain different requirement types. The structure has
 82 been tested with embedded products but not with
 83 CPSS and the authors argue that it has to be tested with
 84 other product types and might require different
 85 categorization.

86 Penzenstadler and Eckhardt [42] agree that ensuring
 87 communication and consistency of requirements for
 88 CPS is a challenge due to the variety of stakeholders
 89 involved. The authors propose a RE content model for
 90 requirements elicitation and documentation at different
 91 levels as a solution. The model originates from a
 92 research project with stakeholders from 30 companies
 93 and characterizes the artefacts that have to be defined
 94 during RE instead of a specific RE process. This leaves
 95 the organization of the RE activities in the hand of each
 96 stakeholder. The content model features five levels
 97 (context, system, subsystem, architecture) with several
 98 items. It has been implemented in the Enterprise
 99 Architect tool based on SysML and UML diagrams.
 100 However this requires the adoption of the content
 101 model for CPSS by all stakeholders involved.

102 Wiesner et al. [43] also address the problem of
 103 information exchange between the different disciplines.
 104 They propose Natural Language Processing (NLP) as a
 105 way to translate non-formal requirements to formal
 106 descriptions in different disciplines, thus enabling
 107 automated information processing. Natural language is
 108 a universal format, understood by the end user and
 109 stakeholders from all involved disciplines. NLP
 110 techniques can assist requirements engineers when
 111 writing specifications. The application of NLP could
 112 establish a dialog system, which supports resolving
 113 ambiguities and semi-automatically transform
 114 requirements in natural language into discipline
 115 specific models. However this theoretical approach has
 116 not yet been tested for CPSS development in practice.

117 Concerning PSS development, recent studies about
 118 how to investigate the customer needs propose the
 119 following approaches among others. The Design

1 Structure Matrix (DSM), can be used to define the main
 2 functions of a PSS. Business Use Case (BUC) analysis
 3 defines the use-case model and a goal-oriented set of
 4 interactions between external actors and the PSS.
 5 Hidden requirements can be elicited using Serious
 6 Games to investigate the PSS life-cycle. Peruzzini et al.
 7 [44] propose a new methodology to support the
 8 preliminary design of a sustainable PSS, based on
 9 quality functional deployment (QFD) approach. It
 10 would allow defining a set of robust requirements for
 11 creating new PSS in respect with the specific customer
 12 needs and the sustainability principles of the industrial
 13 network.

14 The combination of these techniques with a deep
 15 process analysis and related modelling (e.g. UML 2.0)
 16 allows achieving a comprehensive mapping of PSS
 17 tangible and intangible assets. Indeed, process analysis
 18 and modelling allow defining the main activities to
 19 achieve the process tasks, and identifying the
 20 enterprise's ability in capturing and sharing process
 21 knowledge and transferring it. The main common
 22 techniques for process modelling come from static
 23 models, focusing on the information flow (i.e. UML,
 24 Petri- Nets, flowcharting, IDEF0, etc.), till to dynamic
 25 models for process evaluation (i.e. Event-Process
 26 Chain). They are useful for process representation and
 27 performance evaluation, providing a high-technical
 28 view.

29 However, a selection or proposition for approaches
 30 combining the viewpoints of CPS and PSS towards an
 31 integrated RE approach for CPSS is not known to the
 32 authors. It would have to cover technological and
 33 business aspects during requirements take-up and
 34 management. In the following section, two industrial
 35 case studies will be presented, which have developed
 36 CPSS without such a methodology.

37 5. Industrial Case Studies

38 In order to investigate how the RE is applied in
 39 industrial companies to design a CPSS, two case
 40 studies are presented in this paper. They belong to two
 41 different industrial contexts: whitegoods appliances
 42 and plastic extrusion process for pipes. Realizing and
 43 processing two different kinds of CPSS, they address
 44 different stakeholders from various domains, and have
 45 specific challenges to face, according to their business.

46 5.1. CPSS engineering in Whitegoods sector

47 The case study in the whitegoods sector involves a
 48 leading Italian company designing and producing
 49 household appliances, enabling common activities
 50 within a domestic environment (e.g. washing dirty
 51 clothes, drying, freezing food, etc.), which are usually
 52 characterized by high human-product interaction.
 53 Generally, in this sector the company that delivers the
 54 final product is an assembler, and it collaborates with
 55 numerous suppliers and partners. Therefore, the supply
 56 chain is one of the main strategic elements of success.
 57 It is founded on knowledge of the experience and
 58 contribution of technological and business partners
 59 with peculiar skills.

60 The company wants to propose to customers a new
 61 CPSS offer on appliances such as washing machines,
 62 dryers, washing dryers and dishwashers. The service
 63 proposal is named “Smart Maintenance” and aims to
 64 monitor the appliances to check their status in order to
 65 prevent any fault and avoiding a wrong behavior
 66 during customer usage. Delivering this specific kind of
 67 PSS, the company requires to integrate it with the CPS
 68 concept, because the specific services delivered within
 69 the new proposal need an ICT infrastructure (e.g. HW
 70 system composed by new sensors, SW system to
 71 manage the maintenance actions, DBs to data storage,
 72 web/mobile application to deliver the service to
 73 customers, etc.). The company has applied IoT
 74 technology able to connect products in a smart
 75 environment (see Fig. 6.).

76
77

Fig. 6. The Smart Maintenance CPSS

78 This approach introduces the concept of CPSS and
 79 its engineering, because we have not only a product to
 80 convert into a PSS, but also a new process to develop
 81 able to monitor and check the machines status,
 82 efficiency and efficacy. According to this approach,
 83 a series of new partners, such as technology suppliers,
 84 research institutes and consulting companies in
 85 specific innovation activities need to be involved in the
 86 current company ecosystem. The product needs to be
 87 equipped with recent technological components and
 88 advanced user interfaces. Furthermore, the P-SLM
 89 should be redefined, in order to reorganize also the
 90 design and development process to realize the CPSS
 91 and deliver the new offer to customers.

92 In order to reach all these objectives, it is necessary
 93 to identify all the stakeholders and take their
 94 requirements into account. The involved company has
 95 conducted this activity through the application of
 96 Serious Games and BUC approaches.

97 Serious Games helped the company to identify the
 98 main problems in its business routine, to translate them
 99 in meaningful requirements when they emerge. During
 100 the preparation phase, the company's current processes
 101 (AS-IS scenario) have been modeled through the BUC
 102 and analyzed with questionnaires for validating the
 103 AS-IS scenario defined. During the gaming phase, two
 104 main activities have been conducted: a requirements
 105 workshop and online-playing sessions. The main
 106 objective during this phase was the collection of
 107 detailed requirements and the related KPIs to validate
 108 the elicited requirements. Finally, during the review

1 phase, all the data generated during the previous steps
2 is analyzed and checked by both the company's
3 multidisciplinary team involved in this activity and the
4 experts that have conducted the Serious Game to give
5 different attributes to the requirements generated.

6 The RE approaches applied inside the whitegoods
7 company were useful to list the main PSS requirements
8 in order to define the CPSS functionalities and build
9 the related ICT infrastructure. However, the transition
10 from stakeholders' needs and requirements to CPSS
11 architecture and functionalities is not so easy to realize
12 and requests a deep company effort. Such issues are
13 often seen as a barrier by the industrial companies,
14 entailing their distrust in using these RE approaches.

15 5.2. CPSS engineering in Plastic Extrusion sector

16 The case study in plastic extrusion involves an
17 Italian company that realizes and delivers commodities
18 in the infrastructure and construction sectors. Indeed,
19 its core business concerns pipes and junctions in PVC
20 (polyvinyl chloride), PE (polyethylene) and corrugates
21 through the exploitation of the extrusion process.

22 The extrusion process is a high-energy consuming
23 process that works 24 hours for 7 days, while the
24 product is almost a commodity. Therefore, in order to
25 reduce the energy consumption, improve the efficiency
26 of the industrial process and extend the current product
27 life cycle, the company aims to adopt a CPSS concept.
28 Currently, a relevant problem for the company is
29 having non-compliant products due to failures in the
30 different production process steps. Since the internal
31 processes are not efficiently monitored, these problems
32 generally emerge only after the product realization or
33 even after the delivery to customers. First, this leads to
34 a sensible increase of the lead time and a reduction of
35 the final product quality, which it is directly related to
36 customer satisfaction. But especially this kind of
37 problems could cause important economic losses due
38 to the need to stop the continuous production. In this
39 context, the most important challenge for the involved
40 company is to continuously manage the internal
41 processes, sharing the responsibility of this activity
42 with the final customers. To reach this scope, the
43 involved company has adopted a hardware
44 infrastructure within its facilities in order to measure
45 and monitor data of the industrial process. At the same
46 time, the company has involved other stakeholders to
47 realize the software system able to collect and manage
48 the data measured by the process. Its aim was to have
49 a wide vision about the extrusion process and share the
50 main process information with the customer that has
51 commissioned the order processed by that process. In
52 this way, the company will be able to give a clear
53 signal to their customers and competitors that in order
54 to pursue product and process quality, it is also open to
55 share internal information and know-how about
56 products and manufacturing processes. Moreover,
57 monitoring the industrial process not only provides a
58 new service-oriented offer to the customers, but also

59 allows realizing energy efficiency policies on the
60 industrial process (see Fig. 7.).

61
62 **Fig. 7.** The Smart Maintenance CPSS

63 This new company approach entails the adoption of
64 the CPSS, where there is the application of the CPS
65 concept to the industrial process and the promotion of
66 a new service-oriented offer that makes customers
67 more aware about the quality of the product and the
68 related industrial process exploited to realize it.

69 In order to realize this CPSS, it was necessary to
70 identify all the stakeholders and to take their (e.g.
71 customer) requirements into account. The involved
72 company has conducted this activity through the
73 exploitation of BUC and QFD approaches. The BUC
74 was useful to model the CPSS use-case, identifying
75 both the main company and stakeholder purposes, and
76 the interactions' set between external actors and the
77 involved process. Then, the QFD approach supported
78 the definition of the new company's ecosystem,
79 through the map of customer's and other stakeholder's
80 needs, their link with the service functionalities, the
81 recognition of the market demand, the definition of the
82 tangible and intangible assets required. The result was
83 a requirements list that supported the company to
84 identify its new ecosystem and also the new business
85 model to adopt, in order to realize and deliver the CPSS.

86 The RE approaches exploited by the company to
87 design its idea of CPSS has given some positive results,
88 regarding the modeling of the use case in terms of
89 tangible and intangible assets involved, stakeholders
90 required, their needs and the link among them.
91 Moreover, the approaches have mostly focused on the
92 functionalities actually required by customers,
93 designing an effective PSS offer. At the same time, this
94 result allowed identifying only that process parameters
95 actually involved in the delivery of the PSS
96 functionalities required by customers. In this way, also
97 the CPS was optimized.

98 However, the RE approaches have highlighted two
99 main challenges. The first one is about the data and
100 information sharing, because these approaches cannot
101 support the data management among the ecosystem's
102 stakeholders. This represents a weakness because it
103 entails that if the sensitive information from one or
104 more stakeholders cannot be managed during the RE
105 approaches, maybe all the requirements derived and
106 elicited from them are not all the requirements that can
107 be generated. The second challenge is about the
108 difficulty to collect the required information from all

1 the stakeholders involved in the CPSS, due to both the
 2 wide ecosystem dimension, and the complexity of the
 3 approach itself, which requires to collect lot of
 4 information that not all the companies are willing to
 5 share.

6 **6. Requirements Engineering for** 7 **Cyber-physical Product-Service Systems**

8 The mentioned characteristics of CPSS influence
 9 the systems engineering process. As highlighted, CPS
 10 and PSS have their own specific demands on RE
 11 methodology, which have to be integrated for CPSS.
 12 In the following, the challenges identified in literature
 13 and in the two use cases are described.

14 **6.1. Identification of Challenges**

15 Several challenges for engineering CPSS could be
 16 identified, which have to be addressed by a suitable RE
 17 approach. They come from three main areas: the
 18 complexity of the CPSS itself, the distributed
 19 stakeholder environment around the CPSS and the
 20 different disciplines involved in CPSS development.

21 CPSS consist of a large number of different cyber,
 22 physical and service components that create the
 23 desired functionality through emergent behavior.
 24 Furthermore, they are open systems that have to be
 25 interoperable and can evolve. According to Ncube [45],
 26 for interoperation between systems that have been
 27 separately developed, RE has to be able to identify the
 28 key interoperation influencing requirements. Due to
 29 the complexity inherent to systems of systems, such as
 30 CPSS, requirements are distributed among many
 31 disciplines and can be conflicting, unstable,
 32 unknowable or not fully defined. For CPS, Schätz [46]
 33 describes three dimensions of complexity: cross
 34 (application domains, engineering disciplines,
 35 technologies, organizations), live (reconfiguration,
 36 redeployment, update) and self (documentation,
 37 monitoring, adaptation). All of these dimensions also
 38 apply on CPSS and have to be to be considered already
 39 during RE, extended by service development,
 40 provision and evolution.

41 CPSS have a large number of stakeholders that are
 42 typically separated spatially and organizationally. In
 43 addition to the user, who defines the scope and purpose
 44 of the CPSS, specialized partners with distinct
 45 processes develop the individual system components.
 46 Following literature for CPS and PSS [12,47], users
 47 and other stakeholders from different domains have to
 48 be actively involved into the development from the
 49 start. The CPSS has to be adapted to the needs and
 50 competences of its application environment.

51 The stakeholders are not only distributed, they also
 52 stem from multiple disciplines with own formalisms
 53 and tools. During CPSS development, information and
 54 requirements have to be exchanged between the
 55 disciplines in order to create a common view of the
 56 targeted system. Various Authors [11,15] emphasize

57 the need for theories and tools to design, analyse and
 58 verify the components at various levels, understand the
 59 interactions between systems and ensure safety and
 60 performance with minimal cost. Currently, CPSS
 61 components are handled by isolated disciplines, which
 62 either represent the cyber, physical or service process.
 63 This hinders the verification of the overall system
 64 design and component-to-component interaction. The
 65 synthesis of knowledge across different domains of
 66 application, including methods of requirements
 67 analysis and modelling is needed [48].

68 **6.2. Requirements to overcome the Challenges**

69 Based on the challenges identified in the previous
 70 section, requirements for a CPSS RE approach can be
 71 outlined. Requirements in CPSS development process
 72 can be assigned to two distinguished areas: the
 73 problem domain and the solution domain. The problem
 74 domain includes the needs and business goals for
 75 system development and their formulation into
 76 stakeholder requirements, without preselecting any
 77 specific CPSS characteristics. The solution domain
 78 contains the system requirements describing the
 79 targeted functionalities of the solution and
 80 subsequently the architectural design, which specifies
 81 how the CPSS will meet the system requirements.

82 Business requirements can be derived from the
 83 business goals or objectives of the organization, which
 84 interpret the underlying business vision. They are
 85 mostly given in natural language. Methods for
 86 documentation of business requirements can be
 87 Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN) or data
 88 flow diagrams, showing the difference between “as-is”
 89 and “to-be” business processes. Stakeholder
 90 requirements in general are derived from the
 91 statements of need, using various methods like use
 92 scenarios, and are stated in non-technical terms
 93 normally not adequate for design purposes.

94 Describing the targeted CPSS behaviour in terms of
 95 conditions or capabilities of the envisaged solution can
 96 be done through developing system models describing
 97 functionality and then documenting system
 98 requirements that capture the vision of the customer in
 99 technical terms, enable the definition of the scope of
 100 the system and allow estimating the cost and schedule
 101 required to build the system. The description of the
 102 architectural design of a system identifies the different
 103 system elements and shows how they work together
 104 through their relationships to meet the system
 105 requirements. In the case of CPSS, this can be the
 106 interaction between product and services, or between
 107 software and hardware. These models can be
 108 documented in SysML or domain specific notation.

109 As it is often not possible to use a common notation,
 110 such as SysML, for all involved stakeholders, a
 111 mediation or translation has to be established between
 112 the different domain models. For the semi-automatic
 113 translation between non-formal (natural language) and
 114 formalized notations, Natural Language
 115 Processing [43] can be implemented. Transformation

1 between the different formal domain specific models
 2 can be achieved using methods such as semantic
 3 mediation, which enable conversion between model
 4 using ontologies. In this way, domain barriers can be
 5 greatly reduced or fully removed.

6 7. Conclusion and future Work

7 Systems engineering is evolving from a centralized
 8 development process for individual systems and
 9 components towards the orchestration of distributed
 10 software, hardware and business processes for a
 11 common purpose. The scale and complexity of the
 12 objects targeted by systems engineering is constantly
 13 growing, reflected by the emergence of CPS and PSS.
 14 Regarding the first research question, the paper has
 15 presented the state-of-the-art and concepts in these
 16 areas, as well as their combination to Cyber-physical
 17 Product-Service Systems.

18 Answering the second research question, a first
 19 concept for CPSS has been developed. In the paper, it
 20 could be shown that CPSS have special characteristics
 21 compared with CPS and PSS that affect Requirements
 22 Engineering. Existing RE approaches from the CPS
 23 and PSS sector have been identified and adopted in two
 24 industrial use cases for CPSS development.

25 As for the third research question, the analysis
 26 shows that current methods and tools for RE do not
 27 provide full support for the new CPSS challenges. The
 28 main points identified are greater complexity, multiple
 29 distributed stakeholders and the involvement of
 30 several disciplines with their own formalisms and
 31 models, such as product, service and ICT.

32 At the same time, first approaches to address these
 33 issues for Requirements Engineering could be found.
 34 Complexity can be addressed with a suitable
 35 management structure that supports the reuse of
 36 requirements from earlier projects and thus enables
 37 modularization of CPSS. Future work in this area
 38 should include the specification of such a requirements
 39 structure, which also helps to manage changing
 40 requirements and predicts the emerging properties of a
 41 CPSS.

42 Multiple distributed stakeholders for the system as a
 43 whole may have limited knowledge of the needs and
 44 constraints for the individual components, and vice
 45 versa. They can be included by implementing a
 46 universal content model for CPSS that helps to
 47 exchange unambiguous information about the targeted
 48 system requirements. Non-technical stakeholders,
 49 such as the user of the CPSS or service providers could
 50 participate in system development based on natural
 51 language approaches. Future work should extend such
 52 a content model with interfaces to natural language and
 53 domain specific models, where necessary.

54 The involvement of different disciplines requires the
 55 implementation of a common standard, as either
 56 described above or appropriate interfaces between
 57 domain specific and common models. As it might not
 58 be possible to replace domain specific models in all

59 cases, future work should deal with the
 60 implementation of such interfaces that are able to
 61 translate between different models without
 62 information loss or delay. Addressing the identified
 63 requirements with a CPSS Requirements Engineering
 64 framework would help to make the development of
 65 CPSS more cost effective and faster, while retaining a
 66 high system quality.

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